

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Pela Gandong local wisdom as multicultural education model after the Ambon Conflict

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to describe how Pela Gandong as a model of multicultural education has been implemented between the State Junior High School (SMPN) 9 Ambon City and the State Junior High School (SMPN) 4 Salahutu Liang, Central Maluku Regency. The Ambon conflict became a very valuable lesson for the Indonesian people, especially the Ambonese-Maluku people. That the diversity that has been bestowed must be managed properly and is a reality of life. The Ambon conflict is the largest civil conflict based on ethnicity, religion, race and ethnicity (SARA) after the fall of the Suharto government on May 21, 1998. After the Ambon conflict ended, various parties began to think about how to do peacebuilding so that similar conflicts did not happen again. One of them is implementing multicultural education based on the local wisdom values of Pela Gandong. During the Ambon conflict resolution, Pela Gandong's local wisdom became the medium. The research method used is descriptive qualitative with a case study approach. Data was collected by means of literature study, interviews, observation, and document analysis. The results show that Pela Gandong contains multicultural values that have been built by the ancestors of the Maluku people, and is currently uniting Muslim and Christian students with a local cultural approach. The implementation is done by transforming Pela Gandong values in schools and teacher exchanges. Then jointly held; scouting activities, camping, Christmas, iftar, Sports and Arts Week. Both schools were also part of the 2013 film Provocateur of Peace as a campaign for peace and the spread of multicultural values.

Keywords: Local wisdom; pela gandong; multicultural education; Ambon Conflict

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1. Introduction

The Ambon conflict is the largest ethnic, religious, racial and inter-ethnic (SARA) based civil conflict after the fall of President Suharto on May 21, 1998. This can be seen from the Ambon turmoil which resulted in more than 8-9 thousand deaths, 29 thousand houses burned, and 45 mosques, 47 churches, 719 shops, 38 government buildings, and 4 banks were destroyed. The range of conflicts that occurred was also quite long, namely 4 years (Aziz SR, 2019). The Ambon conflict is only one of many conflicts that occur in Indonesia. For example, the Sambas conflict, the Poso conflict, the Sampit conflict, the Bloody Wamena and others, but the Ambon conflict is the biggest and most destructive.

Diversity is a gift that has been given by God and is grateful for (Dietrich, 2018; Burke & McDowell, 2021). But at the same time, if

there is no management of diversity management, then the gift turns into a bloody conflict, and a terrible event; never thought it would happen. Diversity can be a source of conflict if humans are selfish and feel the most right (Martin et al., 2016; Kopnina et al., 2018; Gilbert, 2021). Conflict is a phenomenon that most often arises because conflict has always been a social and political part of human life and has become a driving force in socio-political dynamics and changes.

So that conflicts will always arise when community groups have certain goals and mutually impose their resources (Wiradhika, 2018). Indonesia is a large country with thousands of islands, from Miangas to Rote, and from Sabang to Merauke. The 2010 Population Census stated that there were 1,331 ethnic groups in Indonesia (BPS, 2015). The category is a code for the name of a tribe,